

Deliverable 1.6: Visual identity

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Basic information

Project title	Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers
Project acronym	VISION
Call	H2020-WIDESPREAD-2018-2020
Topic	WIDESPREAD-03-2018
Project type	Coordination and Supporting Action (CSA)
Grant Agreement No.	857381
Nature	DEC
Dissemination level	PU (Public)

Executive summary

Development of a visual identity for the VISION project is one of the most important elements of the project's identity. The VISION project logo is present at all communication documents and templates (deliverables and powerpoint templates). In addition, the VISION project logo along with the logo of the European Union and acknowledgement of EU funding will appear at all documents used in communication and dissemination of project results.

1 VISION logo

The development of the VISION project logo was an early task in the project implementation. The VISION project logo is a combination of text and visual imagery. The text is the acronym of the project in two main solid colours - grey and red. Individual solid circles in the picture symbolize EU countries. Solid circles in red, orange, yellow, green and blue represent countries involved in the project and correspond with the colours of countries at the map in the website heading (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The logo of the VISION project.

2 Template for communication and dissemination

A template for preparing any project deliverable created as the result of work done during a project was prepared.

2.1 Word document template for deliverables

This MS Word document template (Fig. 2) is free to download for all partners from the VISION intranet.

2.2 Word document templates for training activities

Two MS Word document templates will be prepared for the purpose of training/course activities. Both templates will be free to download from the VISION website.

2.2.1 Word document template for Motivation letter

The applicants will use this template to prepare and submit his/her applications (Fig.3).

2.2.2 Word document template for Final report

The applicants will use this template to prepare his/her Final report within 30 days after return from the stay (Fig. 4).

Figure 2. The VISION word document template for Deliverable reports.

Figure 3. The VISION word document template for Motivation letter.

Figure 4. The VISION word document template for Final report.

2.3 Powerpoint template for presentations

This MS PowerPoint template (Fig. 5) is free to download for all partners from the VISION intranet.

Figure 5. The VISION MS PowerPoint template

3 Acknowledgement

Acknowledgement of EU funding together with the logo of the EU flag (Fig. 5) is free to download for all partners from the VISION intranet. It will be present at all lectures, posters and publications prepared during the VISION project implementation.

3.1.1 Publications

The following text will appear in papers published during the VISION project implementation.

“This paper is supported by European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381, project VISION (Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers).“

3.1.2 Presentations & posters

The following text and logo of the EU flag will be present at presentations/posters during the VISION project implementation.

„This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857381, project VISION (Strategies to strengthen scientific excellence and innovation capacity for early diagnosis of gastrointestinal cancers)“